

EARTH SCIENCES

PAPER PACKAGING FOR FOOD PRODUCTS

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Abstract

This article explores innovative solutions for creating eco-friendly paper packaging (PaP) designed for food products. It examines its environmental significance as an alternative to traditional plastic and composite materials, which have negative environmental impacts. The main components ensuring biodegradability and compostability of packaging, including cellulose, vegetable starch and polylactic acid, are analyzed. The article also discusses antibacterial and antimicrobial coatings that can extend the shelf life of products and enhance their safety. The prospects and challenges for manufacturers and consumers in transitioning to eco-friendly materials are considered, along with examples of companies that have successfully implemented such solutions.

Keywords: *paper packaging (PaP), biodegradable materials, compostable packaging, antibacterial coatings, barrier technologies, environmental sustainability.*

Introduction

Given the current environmental situation, it is crucial to find eco-friendly solutions in different sectors. A major focus in this area is the creation of environmentally-friendly packaging for food items. Plastic packaging, commonly utilized in the food sector, has a detrimental impact on the environment because it takes a long time to decompose and is not easily recyclable. On the other hand, paper packaging (PaP) has the ability to decompose naturally and can be used in composting, making it a more appealing option for manufacturers looking to lessen their environmental impact and adhere to sustainable practices.

Consumer demand for eco-friendly products and packaging materials is also pushing the transition to PaP. In recent years, the public has become more aware of the issues linked to too much plastic usage, prompting producers to look for more eco-friendly options. Governments and international organizations are enforcing stringent rules and limitations on the utilization of single-use plastics, pushing companies towards adopting paper-based alternatives. In this situation, the significance of advancements in PaP is growing, as they allow for the enhancement of its functional abilities and guarantee the essential safeguarding of products.

The goal of this research is to analyze modern innovative approaches to creating PaP for food products,

considering its environmental and operational characteristics. Methods of comparative research and systematic literature review, including scientific articles and industry reports, were used to analyze innovative solutions in the field of PaP.

Main part. The environmental significance of PaP

An important role in promoting sustainable development, especially in the context of the global environmental crisis caused by the excessive use of plastic, is played by PaP. One of its main advantages is its **natural biodegradability**, making it a more eco-friendly alternative to plastic and composite materials that contain layers of polymers and metals. Composite materials, for instance, are difficult to recycle due to their multiple layers, which complicates decomposition and recycling. On the other hand, PaP **requires lower recycling costs** because it does not contain toxic elements contained in plastic and is recyclable with minimal waste. Additionally, it leaves a significantly smaller carbon footprint, as paper production requires less energy and water compared to plastic production. According to industry research, in developed countries, the recycling rate for paper materials reaches 68%, which significantly surpasses plastic recycling rates, which often do not exceed 9% (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Recycling rate of paper and plastic, 2022 [1]

The primary environmental concerns linked to traditional packaging materials, like plastic, comprise extended decomposition time, adverse effects on ecosystems, and microplastic contamination. These issues require a transition to sustainable options that not only reduce harm to the environment but also support the principles of a circular economy. In this situation, new PaP stands out as a hopeful answer.

Innovative materials and technologies in PaP

In the last few years, new materials and technologies have been developed to increase the flexibility of PaP in the food industry, addressing worries about the eco-friendliness and functionality of packaging. The main goal in the development of environmentally friendly packaging is the use of **biodegradable and compostable substances** such as cellulose and other organic components. These provide an eco-friendly alternative to traditional packaging as they can fully biodegrade, reducing the strain on landfills and preventing pollution caused by plastic waste that decomposes slowly [2]. The objective in making these materials is to develop packaging that safeguards items while having a small ecological footprint and can return to the ecosystem as natural material.

Cellulose from wood pulp is the main ingredient in numerous environmentally friendly paper products capable of naturally decomposing. Its sturdy fiber structure ensures the longevity of the packaging, while its capacity to decompose organically makes it an eco-friendly choice in comparison to synthetic polymers. Another important factor is the **plant starch**, which enhances the strength and barrier properties of the packaging. It breaks down quickly with the help of microorganisms, allowing packaging containing it to be composted at home. **Polylactic acid (PLA)**, a biodegradable polymer made from corn or sugar-based sources, is commonly applied as a coating on PaP to enhance its ability to withstand moisture and oxygen. It completely breaks down in industrial composting conditions, making it a perfect material for disposable packaging [3]. **Lignin**, a component found in wood cells, improves the mechanical properties of packaging, making it more resistant to moisture and tearing, and is

also an eco-friendly ingredient. Thus, it is crucial to create biodegradable and compostable PaP to produce eco-friendly alternatives that reduce waste and protect the environment, while maintaining qualities such as toughness, usefulness, and safety.

Antibacterial and antimicrobial coatings have been created for PaP in order to inhibit the proliferation of harmful microorganisms and prolong the durability of items, especially those prone to deterioration. Their main objective is to safeguard products from detrimental bacteria, fungi, and mold that may cause deterioration, affect the flavor and quality, and present health hazards for customers. Utilizing antibacterial coatings aids in maintaining food safety and enhancing cleanliness attributes.

Antibacterial and antimicrobial layers are typically created with natural and safe ingredients like herbal extracts (cinnamon, thyme, garlic) as well as silver and copper nanoparticles, which have antimicrobial properties. These substances can disrupt bacterial membranes or impede their growth, ultimately preventing the spread of harmful microorganisms on packaging surfaces. Silver nanoparticles are greatly appreciated for their strong antibacterial effects and their suitability for food items, as they create an invisible shield that prevents the proliferation of harmful microorganisms on the packaging while in use.

Through the use of these coatings, PaP has the ability to serve as a reliable alternative to conventional packaging for perishable goods such as meat, fish, dairy products, and fresh vegetables that require robust protection against microbes. They help reduce the need for additional chemical preservatives, especially important for natural and organic products that require maintaining their composition. These coatings can be applied to the inside and outside of the packaging without affecting its recyclability or composability. The addition of antibacterial and antimicrobial coatings expands the functional abilities of PaP, ensuring product freshness and safety. The food industry has an increasing demand for eco-friendly packaging solutions using this technology.

Barrier technologies in PaP provide effective protection for products against negative impacts of external elements like moisture and oxygen, preventing spoilage and taste deterioration. Coatings made from natural waxes, plant starch, resins, proteins, and polysaccharides are some of the most frequently used. Wax coatings, such as, efficiently block moisture without increasing weight and are eco-friendly while maintaining product safety [4]. Plant starch is utilized to form a barrier against oxygen, increasing product longevity and maintaining freshness naturally, without the need for synthetic preservatives. Depending on the level of protection needed, these coatings can be used on both the inside and outside of the packaging.

Aside from conventional coatings made from natural materials, biopolymers like PLA and polyethylene furanoate (PEF) are commonly utilized. They form a slim barrier that is very durable against moisture and oxygen and completely biodegradable in industrial settings. These coatings help to maintain the longevity and seal of the packaging, even in tough storage conditions like refrigeration or freezing.

Plastic-free barrier coatings are crucial for sustainable packaging, offering both strong product protection

and the option to recycle or compost the packaging post-use. These technologies enable PaP to become a complete substitute for plastic and composite materials, adhering to sustainable production principles and decreasing plastic waste.

Nanotechnology offers new possibilities for improving the strength, durability, and functionality. Its use in PaP manufacturing enhances efficiency while still preserving environmental advantages, increasing its popularity in the food sector and allowing packaging to conform to current market demands.

Analysis of prospects and challenges in the transition to environmentally friendly materials

With the ongoing global environmental crisis, it is especially important for manufacturers and consumers to shift towards using eco-friendly materials. The demand for sustainable solutions is driven by pollution caused by excessive plastic use and other materials that are difficult to degrade, in order to reduce environmental impact. The introduction of biodegradable and compostable packaging has become an important focus of this transition, as it can decompose naturally and reduce waste. However, switching to eco-friendly materials comes with various prospects and challenges (table 1).

Table 1.

Prospects and challenges in transitioning to eco-friendly paper materials [5, 6]

Category	The prospects	Challenges
Manufacturers	The growth of consumer demand for eco-friendly products	High costs for the introduction of new technologies
	Government support	The need to upgrade equipment
	Reducing the carbon footprint	Limited availability of raw materials and technology opportunities
Consumers	Health safety	Increasing the cost of products
	Reducing the ecological footprint	Insufficient infrastructure for recycling
	Promoting sustainable consumption	Limited number of products available

The shift to environmentally friendly paper materials in the packaging sector offers substantial chances for sustainable growth, enabling businesses to improve their green reputation and appeal to eco-conscious customers. Although facing obstacles like rising expenses and the requirement for technological adjustments, the benefits of eco-friendly packaging are becoming increasingly clear and sought after. Leading companies' experiences demonstrate that integrating innovative solutions not only reduces environmental impact but also enhances brand presence in today's market.

For instance, **McDonald's** is slowly switching from plastic packaging to paper, such as cups, lids, and packaging for hot items. The company has started using paper straws instead of plastic ones, showing its dedication to cutting down on plastic waste. McDonald's aims to have all of its packaging made from renewable or recycled materials [7].

Another instance is **Starbucks**, making efforts to decrease plastic usage and introduce environmentally friendly packaging. The company provides paper cups in addition to cardboard and paper bags for its products. Starbucks is experimenting with options other than plastic lids and striving to utilize compostable and recyclable materials in order to reduce its environmental impact [8].

The experiences of these companies demonstrate that switching to PaP is not just a green choice, but also a smart tactic for gaining consumer trust as sustainability becomes a top priority for many.

Conclusion

The adoption of PaP for food products is an important step towards sustainable development. Unlike traditional plastic materials, it not only decomposes in natural conditions, but also supports the principles of a closed-loop economy. Innovations in PaP technology, like eco-friendly coatings, protective layers, and antimicrobial substances, help safeguard products and prolong shelf life with reduced harm to the environment.

The move towards sustainable packaging is motivated by increasing consumer demands and stringent regulations targeting the reduction of plastic pollution. Even though there are obstacles like the requirement for new technology investments and possible cost rises, the advantages of adopting environmentally friendly packaging options are becoming clearer. Large companies have found that utilizing sustainable packaging not only boosts brand positioning and increases consumer trust, but also supports global sustainable development objectives. Therefore, PaP for food items is more than just another option, as it effectively addresses the requirement for product protection while also taking care of the environment. Switching to environmentally

friendly packaging materials is increasingly vital for companies looking to uphold sustainable production and responsible consumption practices.

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